

Probability of coincidence in disease selection for consecutive years in Colombia and between Colombia and Central America, 1985-86.^a

Disease	Colombia ^b	Central America	χ^2
Leaf blast	0.83	0.88	1.54 (0.1 < P < 0.9)
Leaf scald	0.93	0.85	2.75 (0.05 < P < 0.1)
Brown spot	–	0.79	–

^aProbability of coincidence: probability for a line to be selected in those locations in Central America with moderate to severe disease levels, given that it was selected in Colombia. ^bBS pressure was too low in 1986; thus no selection was made.

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Rice cultures with early plant resistance to bacterial blight (BB)

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye, a serious disease of wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh, is more damaging during the early crop season when temperature and atmospheric humidity are very high. Only the prebooting stage of long-duration varieties coincides with this period.

We tested a number of cultures for prebooting stage resistance to BB during 1986-87 wet season. Each entry was sown in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with a suspension of a local BB isolate at tillering and rated at 15 d and 30 d after inoculation. TN1 at maximum tillering was the susceptible check.

Eight test cultures had disease scores of 2, 15 had scores of 3 (see table). □

Rice cultures showing early (prebooting stage) plant resistance to local BB pathogen isolate. Faizabad, U. P., India, 1986.

Variety or culture	Cross	Disease ^a score
RP1860-102-23-4-3	IET5656/Salamat	2
MTU7633	VasistalMahsuri	2
CR210-1018	Pankaj/Jagannath	2
CR98-7269	L. Z. Nira/TN1	2
CR260-131-5	CR151/CR1014	2
OR142-29	Pankaj/Sigadis	2
OR142-93	Pankaj/Sigadis	2
OR151-17	Hema/CR51-1523//Vikram	2
CR149-7171-271	MNP36/CR12//Pankaj	3
CR149-206	CR63-5218-1/Pankaj	3
CR98-8081	L. Z. Nira/TN1	3
MTU5182	MTU4569/ARC6650	3
CN836-3-6	–	3
CN836-3-8	–	3
CR376-KR-1	–	3
CR376-KR-2	–	3
CR376-KR-3	–	3
RAU83-8-4	BR-51-46-51/Mahsuri	3
RP1859-206-6-4-2-1	Swarnadhan/Benong III	3
RP1860-249-3-1-1	Swarnadhan/Salamat	3
RP1641-11-5-1-B	Vikram/Bulu Benong III	3
RP1641-44-7	–	3
RP1641-144-11-B	–	3
TN1 (check)	–	3

^aBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980).

Insect resistance

Gall midge (GM) resistance in traditional rice varieties in Bihar

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Seven local rice varieties collected from endemic GM areas of Chhotanagpur plateau, Bihar, were evaluated for resistance in 1984-86 wet seasons. Two resistant and one susceptible high-yielding varieties were included for

comparison. One-month-old seedlings were planted in 3- × 4-m plots with 3 replications. Silvershoot percentage was recorded at peak infestation (45 d after transplanting).

Local variety Baghpanjar consistently showed resistant reactions comparable to those of resistant checks RD202 and Shakti (Table 1). When 3-yr data were pooled, all varieties except Dhusri were better than Jaya. Baghpanjar matched the resistant checks. However, susceptible Jaya recorded the highest yield (Table 2). □

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